

SIMULATION OF THE EVOLUTION OF ECONOMIC-FINANCIAL INDICATORS IN A ROMANIAN ORGANIZATION

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Abstract

Purpose – *The purpose of this paper is to make a financial diagnosis based on accounting data from 2016-2021, in a Romanian organization.*

Methodology/approach - *The financial risk diagnosis aims at measuring the variability of the company's result when changing the company's activity, changing the structure of and the variability of the company's solvency, its capacity to honor the obligations assumed towards third parties.*

Findings – *The company presents a relatively stable situation, which makes it attractive to shareholders and investors in the conditions of paying due attention to the identified risks.*

Research limitations/implications – *Risk analysis and financial profitability analysis are the two basic components of a company's financial diagnosis. A lending company must systematically bear the related financial expenses (interest), which means an increase in its commitments and implicitly the risk.*

Practical implications – *The analysis indicates that the Romanian society in which the study was started is being balanced, its position on the market being strongly influenced by the macro-economic and political situation in Romania regarding agriculture.*

Originality/value – *The choice of the research topic in the field of risk management was justified on the one hand by the novelty of this field, by the increasing theoretical and applied concerns of the profile organizations, and on the other hand by the need to elaborate complex strategies. at the level of the organization, to ensure its protection against the influences of various factors.*

Key words: *financial diagnosis, organization, economic indicators.*

Introduction

In the implementation of a risk management system at the level of an organization there are three possible levels: basic, medium, and advanced (Albu, 2018). The differentiation is made according to the risk attitude of the company's management, the risky field of activity in which it operates, the need for protection expressed by the company's stakeholders, and the company's experience in ensuring the operation of such a system. 2018; Babii, 2020).

While the basic level only proceeds to the occasional identification of risks and their qualitative assessment, the advanced level involves the use of complex mathematical models assisted by

specialized software packages for periodic risk analysis, as well as the creation of a specialized structure within the organization chart (Oliver, 2020).

In this paper, the focus is on making a financial diagnosis based on accounting data obtained from a Romanian organization during the years 2016-2021. In this context, several critical success factors must be considered that influence the effectiveness of risk management (Ranjbar and Amanollahi, 2018). Respectively, it is recommended that it: be an ongoing process integrated into the organization's strategy; consider all risks affecting the activities of the organization; be integrated into the culture of the organization; to translate the strategy into tactical and operational objectives, designating the responsibilities of each manager and employee involved in risk management, as part of the job description.

Regarding the long-term effects of risk management, the author's view is that after implementation, it should be constantly updated due to rapid progress in specific concepts and working tools. These elements argue the need for regular evaluation of the performance and efficiency of the risk management process.

Financial diagnosis of the last 6 years of activity

Analysis of the structure of the balance sheet assets and liabilities

In the literature, issues related to balance sheet assets and liabilities have been addressed by Akyüz (2021) and Lilia (2021).

Regarding the studied organization, in the first two years analyzed (2018 and 2019) the organization recorded a significant share of current assets in total assets, especially stocks of raw materials, finished production and goods (34% and 42%). Given the object of activity of the company and the low evolution of the profile market, this situation can be considered normal. For the next three years, the share of raw material stocks, finished production and goods decreases to 24%, reaching 15%, due to the acquisition of property, plant, and equipment.

Table 1. Summary of the structure of the balance sheet assets and liabilities

No.	BALANCE SHEET INDICATORS	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
1	Fixed assets	0.34	0.32	0.54	0.49	0.54	0.54
1.1	Tangible fixed assets	0.34	0.31	0.54	0.48	0.54	0.54
2	Current assets	0.64	0.66	0.45	0.48	0.45	0.46
2.1	Stocks (sqm, production	0.3422	0.415	0.238	0.195	0.15	0.44
2.2	Receivables (commercial,	0.2991	0.246	0.208	0.288	0.300	0.55
2.3	House and bank accounts	0.016	0.019	0.011	0.030	0.014	0.01
	TOTAL ASSETS	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
3	Equity - CPR	0.27	0.31	0.68	0.67	0.60	0.56
3.1	Paid subscribed capital	0.093	0.084	0.176	0.202	0.200	0.313
3.2	Revaluation reserves	0	0	0.403	0.358	0.295	0.583
3.3	Reserves	0.102	0.142	0.065	0.044	0.060	0.104
4	Long-term debt (> 1 year)	0.0581	0.0244	0.0055	0.0020	0.820	0.076
4.1	Amounts owed to credit institutions	0.0481	0.0223	0.0039	0.0000	0.0000	0.076
5	Current debts (<1 year)	0.58	0.58	0.28	0.30	0.26	0.361
5.1	Amounts owed to credit institutions	0.29	0.39	0.21	0.19	0.15	0.206
5.3	Trade debts	0.12	0.15	0.060	0.094	0.09	0.081
	Permanent capital	0.33	0.34	0.68	0.67	0.68	0.639
	Total debts	0.64	0.60	0.29	0.30	0.34	0.361
	TOTAL LIABILITIES	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

Total fixed assets are at acceptable levels in the first two years (34% and 32%, respectively), but in the second half of the analyzed period there are significant increases, the level exceeding 50%. It can be considered that this increase in fixed assets means a reduction in the company's flexibility, but most of the assets of tangible assets, in the category of land and construction (67% and 70% respectively) indicate a consolidation of the position in the region. In this way, the company is covered against the risk of losing the space needed to carry out the activity and the inability to expand and develop.

The level of receivables throughout the analyzed period is high, registering only a slight decrease in the third year (21%). The availabilities register an average weight of approximately 1% in the whole period, except for the year 2018, when their volume amounted to 3%. The two assets indicate an unsatisfactory liquidity situation, for the compensation of which short-term financing loans were contracted.

The share of equity is low, reaching a level of about 30% in the first two years of analysis. A potential explanation for this situation can be given by the absence of the revaluation of assets severely affected by inflation, a decision that also involves an undervaluation of Kuprina's equity (2020). Over the next two years, the share of equity jumped to about 68%. This situation can be explained in correlation with the previous observation regarding the revaluation of assets. Thus, the documents provided show that in the period 2018-2020, revaluations of assets were carried out, which also determined the correct assessment of the value of equity.

The level of total liabilities in the balance sheet liabilities is high (60-64%) in the first two years analyzed, the majority share being held by operating liabilities, especially short-term loans (30-40%). The need to take out short-term loans is a direct consequence of the high level of receivables, i.e., the inability to collect the amounts due from the sale of products.

The next period under review is marked by a significant reduction in total debt, reaching 34% (2020), due to the repayment of a significant part of long-term loans. The majority share, in total debts, is also held by operating debts, especially short-term loans (28-30%) necessary to finance the current activity, in the conditions of a high level of receivables (28%).

The analysis indicates that the analyzed company is in the process of balancing, its market position being strongly influenced by the macro-economic and political situation in Romania regarding agriculture, especially following the accession to the European Union.

Analysis of working capital indicators

The total working capital expresses the total need to finance the current operating activity, at the level of current assets (Rahmini et al., 2021). During the analyzed period, there is a significant fluctuating annual increase of the equilibrium indicator.

Figure 1. The evolution of the total working capital

An evolution of the total working capital was identified in the organization as a direct consequence of the evolution of current assets. Thus, these, mostly stocks of finished products and trade receivables, have an increasing evolution, throughout the analyzed period, indicating certain difficulties in the process of sale and in the collection of receivables. However, the situation presented is not a cause for concern,

because in case of need, consistent stocks can be obtained by liquidating stocks and recovering receivables.

Liquidity and solvency analysis

In the first two years of analysis, the financing of stocks through the working capital registered low values (0.3%, respectively 8%), but in the rest of the period it had a strong ascending evolution (59% and 95%). In the first case, it is possible for stocks to be financed on account of operating debts, which is not a problem if relations with suppliers of raw materials and consumables are stable.

The second situation indicates a prudent stockpile financing policy, as a direct consequence of the change in development strategy for the next five years.

Current (general) liquidity is below the 2 (recommended) value throughout the analyzed period, but from 2018 to 2019 the indicator shows a significant increase. based on the capitalization of short-term assets, such as by collecting the value of finished products from a manufacturing cycle (possible situation for the company, which covers only 20% of a still developing market).

To quickly identify the liquidity status, the Immediate Liquidity indicator should be around 0.8. In the period 2016-2018, the values of the indicator were reduced (0.4-07), but increasing, reaching in 2020, the value of 0.98. For this reason, it can be considered that the situation of the company is excellent in relation to the recommended level.

In economic terms, this indicator shows the company's ability to meet short-term payments due (current liabilities), only on assets easily convertible into liquidity (receivables and other treasury assets).

However, the mere existence of receivables from customers is not sufficient to cover overdue debts. The phenomenon of claims on some litigious business partners, or bad payers is still a reality of the domestic market, which is why the Liquidity at sight indicator provides more conclusive information on the risks of default.

Thus, for the entire analyzed period, the organization records values between 0.03 and 0.1, well below the recommended level of 0.2. Putting the indicator at these low levels means a high risk in terms of the possibility of covering immediate debts, only through treasury assets (the most liquid assets). The situation can be rectified by better managing customer and supplier relationships, by reducing payment terms for customers and by obtaining more relaxed payment terms from suppliers.

The general solvency ratio is super unitary for the entire analyzed period, in the last three years even registering high values up to 3.8. This rate measures the risk of non-payment of debt, which in the case of the company is non-existent, its total assets being more than sufficient to cover current debts.

Analysis of financial balance

From the point of view of financial autonomy, the company registers values very close to 1, in 2019 it will be 0.997. This situation indicates a declining indebtedness, due to the repayment of long-term loans contracted in previous years and the increase of equity through issues of shares, or revaluations (Sun, 2021). The evolution is normal for a developing company.

In the first two years of analysis, the debt ratio is 0.12 - 0.15 above the recommended value - 0.5, but then the values of the indicator decrease to 0.34 in 2020. The financial significance of the indicator refers to the debt ratio total and total assets of the company, this being optimal the lower. In the case of the company, the debt rate of 2016 and 2017 is a direct result of the contracted operating debts, and in the following years the decrease is due to the reduction of long-term debts and the increase of total assets, the level of short-term debts registering insignificant increases.

The indebtedness of the company decreases from 17.5% in 2016 to 0.3% in 2019 but increases rapidly to 12.09% the following year. The indicator provides information like the Debt Rate, but from the perspective of the company's permanent capital. Compared to the recommended level - maximum 0.5, the values recorded by the company show a low degree of indebtedness, which indicates its ability to contract long-term loans.

Regarding the interest coverage in the period 2016 - 2019, the values are fluctuating, but super unitary thus highlighting the company's ability to pay interest on net profit. In 2017 and 2018, due to negative values, the indicator is not relevant.

In 2020, due to a lower net profit compared to 2019 and an increase in interest expenses, the interest coverage decreases to 0.73. However, it is not a warning sign, as the company is running refurbishment and development programs, financed by bank loans, designed to supplement sales in the next period.

The evolution of earnings per share registers a continuous decrease in the period 2016-2020 with a slight increase in 2019.

Figure 2. Evolution of earnings per share

Analysis of operating expenses in relation to turnover

The company produces agricultural machinery and equipment, products that require various raw materials and consumables and in large quantities. For this reason, expenditures on raw materials and consumables are high in relation to turnover (36-49%).

Staff costs also account for a significant share of turnover. They have a moderately increasing evolution (25-30%), being largely influenced by socio-economic policies at national level and by the change of the staff structure throughout the analyzed period. It is worth mentioning that, due to the type of production of the company, over 50% of the staff is represented by directly productive workers.

The third category of expenses that has a significant share of turnover are those for works and services performed by third parties (13 - 15.5%). The activity of the company involves maintenance and repair expenses, study and research expenses, management and rent expenses, insurance premium expenses, expenses with collaborators, commissions, fees, protocol, advertising, transport, travel, secondments, postal and telecommunications taxes, banking, etc. (Nariswari & Nugraha, 2020).

Given the size of the entire activity of the company, the level recorded by the expenses for the works and services performed is acceptable.

The other elements of expenses have low shares in the turnover and have a stable evolution, considering the size of the company.

Total operating expenses have an increasing evolution in the period 2016 - 2021, exceeding the level of turnover, except for 2019 when there is a significant decrease, close to the level of 2016.

Figure 3. Total operating expenses

Self-financing capacity

This indicator reflects the volume of potential financing resources created by the company in the management of its business, some of which can be allocated to finance future activity (García-Sánchez, 2021). The self-financing capacity of the analyzed company is low in the first and last year of analysis, registering high values in the period 2017-2018. The annual decrease of the financing capacity in the period 2019 - 2020, is largely due to the investment, modernization and development policy adopted by the company in 2018.

Figure 4. Self-financing capacity

The information of the previous indicator must be analyzed in correlation with the actual self-financing, to describe as accurately as possible, the performance of the company. Thus, figure 5 shows that the company opted for a total profit reinvestment policy in the period 2016 - 2018, and in 2019 and 2020 it distributed on average only 6% of the total profit, keeping the difference in reserves. This decision had the consequences of increasing the self-financing capacity for 2020, the self-financing policy being severely affected in 2021 amid the general economic decline.

Figure 5. The evolution of self-financing

Analysis of the company's activity

The company's activity is measured by the recovery time of the management element by turnover and by the number of recoveries from turnover. Thus, the following conclusions can be drawn about the analyzed company.

The asset has an increasing duration of rotation reaching 652 days in 2020. As a result of the investment programs carried out in the last two years, the total assets have also increased, thus the company, having in its patrimony lands, constructions, and high value equipment. For this reason, the asset recovery period is considered normal, as is the number of revolutions (0.56).

The above is also confirmed by the rotation of fixed assets, which have an upward trend, with small fluctuations throughout the analyzed period. The number of rotations is between 3 and 5 for 2018-2017 and on average a single rotation, for the next three years. The situation presented is a good signal for the company's activity because it indicates an efficient management of fixed assets, in the sense that they generate a higher level of turnover.

Normally, the rotation of liabilities is the same as that of assets, the explanation in this case being the increase in share capital, a high level of reserves and total debt.

The stocks have quite long rotation times due to the existence of stocks without movement, as well as the intensification of the activity in the last analyzed period. It should be noted that a large share in the total stocks have the finished products and the goods. It is very possible that this situation will be determined by the production cycle specific to the organization's activity, by some contracts with a duration longer than a financial year, which has consequently the production on stock and the anticipation of the growth of the market in the next period.

Receivables are recovered after a very large number of days, which indicates a relaxed customer policy, as well as the existence of bad creditors, or those who are unable to pay. The situation worsens in 2020, reaching 192 days for the recovery of customers.

Cash flow analysis

The operating activity results in a positive cash flow in the period 2017-2020. This situation is favored by a higher net profit in the last three years of analysis, by a positive change in working capital requirements as well as by the increase in depreciation expenses occasioned by investments in fixed assets in the last period.

Figure 6. Evolution of cash flows

The cash flow for investments has negative values and has a decline between 2017 and 2018, due to the endowment with new equipment and the acquisition of other tangible assets. In 2019, its value became positive due to the reduction of investments and due to the sale of fixed assets, thus increasing the level of revenues from investment activity.

The financing activity was productive throughout the analyzed period, the values of cash flows in this field being always positive and consistent, especially in the period 2018-2019. This situation means the supply of treasury accounts with funds attracted from shareholders and creditors, respectively capital increases, and the contracting of bank loans (Soboleva et al., 2018).

Analysis of profitability indicators

The financial profitability of the company has an oscillating evolution, starting from 34% in 2016, reaching 6.63% in 2020. In other words, the financial profitability decreased from 3.43 lei net result / 1 lei equity to 0.663 lei net result / 1 leu equity. The decrease in efficiency is mainly due to the increase in equity during the period under review, given the reduction in net operating income, especially in 2017 and 2018.

Economic profitability is low, showing a significant decline in 2016-2020, with a slight return in 2019. The indicator measures the efficiency of economic assets through net operating income. Thus, in 2003, 1.48 lei per 1 lei of economic assets were obtained (maximum of the period), in 2018 (minimum of the period) 0.39 lei / 1 lei of economic assets and 0.51 lei per / 1 lei of economic assets in 2020. The most likely cause for declining profitability is most likely the acquisition of fixed assets and the increase in equity, especially in the last two years of analysis (Abeyrathna & Priyadarshana, 2019).

The values of the company's economic and financial profitability must be compared with the profitability in the sector in which it operates, as well as with those of competitors to create an overview of performance (Haldane & Chowla, 2021).

Regarding the evolution of variable operating expenses, there is an increase in the period 2016-2017, the majority share being held by expenditures on raw materials and consumables. Correlating with the intensification of production activity in 2017, this evolution is perfectly justified. At the same time, fixed expenditures increased slightly, mainly due to investments in fixed assets.

Figure 7. Evolution of variable expenditures and fixed expenditures

In the period 2017-2019, the variable expenses decrease sharply, so that in 2020 they will register a level close to that of 2017. The stabilization of the production program and the rigorous management of the operating costs justify this evolution to the greatest extent. Also, another important factor was the refurbishment of the production sections, which determined the reduction of specific costs such as energy consumption, water, maintenance. The increase of fixed expenses registers a fluctuating evolution, as a direct effect of the increase of depreciation expenses, but in the period 2018 - 2020 they know a continuous increase. Their level greatly influences the critical point of profitability.

Figure 8. Evolution of turnover at the break-even point

Conclusions

Following this financial diagnosis, the following conclusions are presented below.

The payment policy of the suppliers makes it possible to ensure free financial resources in each month of activity. An important aspect and at the same time a strong point is the changes identified in the structure of fixed assets, in the sense of refurbishment and modernization of production sections.

Investments in fixed assets such as land and buildings offer stability and the possibility of obtaining additional income in exceptional situations, knowing that the real estate market is experiencing an accelerated development.

Increasing equity is another identified strength. Low indebtedness means adequate management of loans and the possibility of receiving advantageous loans in the future.

A long-term financial equilibrium could be identified. The low share of overheads in total expenses indicates the existence of adequate cost management. Overall solvency is satisfactory.

The existence of own patents and trademarks has also been identified. There is a high level of trade receivables as well as long recovery times. Own resources are reduced in volume and are not sufficient to finance the current activity. Liquidity is low and total operating expenses are high compared to turnover.

There is some old, energy-intensive, low-capacity machinery and equipment, and the large industrial park requires additional maintenance costs.

Acceleration of the turnover rate of stocks of finished products has been identified because of the expansion of the internal and external market. It has been identified to reduce the recovery period of trade receivables by improving customer policies. Investing in the company's image, consolidating its own brands in the market, and using the reputation of licensed brands is an opportunity for improvement, along with outsourcing activities to obtain lower total costs and the emergence of alternative energy suppliers on the market.

Aspects that endanger society concern the instability of economic and fiscal policies at the national level and the uncertainty regarding the future evolution of the agricultural sector at the national level.

Lack of financial risk management in general management can have long-term negative consequences, including bankruptcy

The analysis conducted for the period 2016-2021 indicates that the analyzed company is financially stable and has real prospects for development.

On the one hand, the company has many strengths that can be exploited for future business, but on the other hand, it faces difficulties in terms of debt recovery and management of stocks of raw materials, finished products and production in course.

Also, its activity is still dependent on the situation in the agricultural sector and on macroeconomic policies on agriculture, both domestic and foreign (with a view to intensifying exports to Russia).

The forecast activity indicates a steady increase in economic performance, but which can be further improved by reorganizing the business.

In this sense, it is recommended to change the management of receivables and stocks of raw materials, outsource large activities consuming financial resources to specialized companies, sell unnecessary fixed assets (halls, fixed assets, etc.), ensure the activity against the most common categories of risks, the adoption of production methods meant to streamline the activity (Six Sigma, Lean Production, just in time, etc.).

The investment program started in 2018, continued in the period 2019-2020, generated beneficial consequences for the future activity.

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